

The inclined throw in a medium (gas,air) at larger distances

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We introduce:

a = angle of throw $0^\circ \leq a \leq 90^\circ$
 v_0 = initial velocity
 g = earth's acceleration

We treat the incline throw in a medium (air,gas) with constant density. For throws it is valid see Budo [1] §16 p.85 equation (22):

$$m\ddot{x} = -F(v) \cdot \frac{\dot{x}}{v}$$

$$m\ddot{y} = -mg - F(v) \cdot \frac{\dot{y}}{v}$$

with:

v = absolute value of the velocity

$$v(t) = |(\dot{x}, \dot{y})| := \sqrt{\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2}$$

t = time

m = mass of the ball

$F(v)$ = drag force in medium

The point over x and y means differentiation to the time.

If we calculate very exactly we must use instead of g the acceleration $g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_K}\right)$, see Budo [1] §16 p.85. It is:

φ_F = density of the medium (air,gas)

φ_K = density of the body (ball)

At larger velocity $F(v) = rv^2$ is inserted. r is a certain constant. This case is treated at Timmermann [6], Parker [7] and Kooy [8]. At Budo [1] §16 p.85,86, at Kamke [3] p.624 Nr.9-17 and at Lohr [5] p.197-205 is indicated what is done in this case. In this case there are only numerical solutions. But we have the possibility to simplify the differential equation system. We transform the differential equation system:

$$\begin{aligned} m\ddot{x} &= -r\dot{x} \cdot \sqrt{\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2} \\ m\ddot{y} &= -mg - r\dot{y} \cdot \sqrt{\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2} \end{aligned}$$

Now we simplify the system:

$$m\ddot{x} = -r\dot{x}^2 \quad (1)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} m\ddot{y} &= -mg - r\dot{y}^2 \quad \text{during the ascent} \\ m\ddot{y} &= -mg + r\dot{y}^2 \quad \text{during the descension} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This system is solved at Heuser [2] p.596. We have:

$$x(t) = \frac{m}{r} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{rv_0 \cos a}{m} \cdot t + 1 \right)$$

and

$$y(t) = \frac{m}{r} \cdot \left(\ln \cos \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t - c \right) - \ln \cos c \right) \quad \text{for} \quad 0 \leq t \leq T$$

respectively

$$y(t) = \frac{m}{r} \cdot \left(-\ln \cosh \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t - c \right) - \ln \cos c \right) \quad \text{for} \quad T \leq t \leq \text{time of impact}$$

with:

$$c = \arctan \left(\sqrt{\frac{r}{mg}} \cdot v_0 \sin a \right)$$

and

$$T = \sqrt{\frac{m}{rg}} \cdot c$$

We derive:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= \frac{m}{r} \cdot \left(\frac{rv_0 \cos a}{m} \cdot t + 1 \right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{rv_0 \cos a}{m} \\ &= v_0 \cos a \cdot \left(\frac{rv_0 \cos a}{m} \cdot t + 1 \right)^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{y} &= \frac{m}{r} \cdot \left(\cos \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t - c \right) \right)^{-1} \cdot (-1) \cdot \sin \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t - c \right) \cdot \sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \\ &= -\sqrt{\frac{mg}{r}} \cdot \tan \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t - c \right) \quad \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq T\end{aligned}$$

The calculation in the case $T \leq t \leq$ impact time is similar. The time of ascent can be calculated with $\dot{y} = 0$. If we insert the time of ascent at $y(t)$, we get the height of ascent. Now we want to determine the time of throw t_w with $y(t)=0$:

$$0 = -\ln \cosh \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t_w - c \right) - \ln \cos c$$

It follows:

$$\ln \cosh \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t_w - c \right) = -\ln \cos c = \ln \left(\frac{1}{\cos c} \right)$$

We obtain:

$$\cosh \left(\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t_w - c \right) = \frac{1}{\cos c}$$

We construct the inverse function:

$$\sqrt{\frac{rg}{m}} \cdot t_w - c = \cosh^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\cos c} \right)$$

We get:

$$t_w = \sqrt{\frac{m}{rg}} \cdot \left(\cosh^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\cos c} \right) + c \right)$$

If we insert t_w at $x(t)$, we get the range of throw.

We want to calculate T in an example. For $a=45$ degree and $v_0=100$ metres per second we yield $T= 4.6048$ seconds. We determine the value of $r = c_w \cdot 0.5\pi R^2 \cdot$ (density of air) to 0.0000203 see Kuchling [4] p.165 (M 10.20). R is the ball's radius and c_w the drag coefficient (at the ball=0.1-0.4). The ball's radius shall be 0.01m and the mass 0.004189 kg. The trajectory of projection is shown in the figure.

The maximum velocity at trajectories of projection with quadratic drag function is 200 metres per second.

References

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